

Chapter 12. National Standards and Regulations¹

This chapter focuses on national standards, guidelines and regulations for TVET in SSA. We know of only a few efforts to introduce transnational regulations for TVET. The research literature does not provide much insight into these areas. Therefore, we had to gather information mainly from sources on the internet (government websites). Some states in SSA have informative, well-structured and well-maintained websites on all aspects of their TVET systems. However, there are also government agencies (e.g., in Ethiopia) where this information was hardly, if at all, available on the internet. In some cases, aspects of TVET were also identified via privately operated websites.

The countries considered in particular detail in this chapter include Botswana, Ghana, Kenya, Malawi, Mauritius, Nigeria, Tanzania, Uganda and South Africa, with occasional reference to Namibia, Rwanda and Zambia. As detailed in Chapter 3, we have selected these SSA states according to how frequently they are mentioned in the relevant publications, and on the basis of evidence of their (efforts towards) dual systems.

Research questions considered in this chapter

The research questions considered in this chapter are listed in the box below.

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Research questions considered in this chapter

RQ18. National standards and policies.

[RQ18.a] Which countries have **national standards** for TVET? How were they produced and to whom do they apply? E.g., students, educators, educators located at the workplace, pedagogy specialists, institutions.

[RQ18.b] How are national TVET standards **monitored**? To what extent do data collection and policy planning tools exist at national or regional levels?

[RQ18.c] Within these countries, which **state authorities** are involved in TVET?

[RQ18.d] To what extent / how have **national TVET systems been formalised** (i.e., embedded in the formal education or employment system)? To what extent are the described forms of training integrated into the formal system of the respective country? What measures were recommended and possibly implemented in this regard?

Conclusions of this chapter

Botswana, Ghana, Kenya, South Africa, Nigeria, Uganda, Mauritius and Malawi all have national qualifications frameworks for education. Such qualifications set minimum requirements for the classification, registration and accreditation of national qualifications and certificates. In some countries (Kenya, Ghana, Uganda and Tanzania), these frameworks also provide pointers to pedagogical approaches to be followed. In each of these countries, competence-oriented education is recommended.²

TVET-specific qualification frameworks were found only in Botswana, Ghana and Uganda. Our research found that Botswana, Kenya, Uganda and South Africa strategically plan and develop TVET. In South Africa, for example, the training of teachers for TVET is conducted by the state.

Strategic Community Review (SCR) participant Amon Haufiku (Namibia Training Authority), mentioned that the Southern African Development Community (SADC) has developed a qualification framework to ensure free mobility and recognition of member countries'³ qualification frameworks, ensuring proper alignment between the different nations.

Our internet search and policy analysis show that most of the countries in SSA have government agencies responsible for the accreditation of TVET programmes and TVET institutions. In Ghana, Kenya, South Africa, Mauritius, Nigeria and Uganda, state guidelines are issued for any TVET offered.

Information is provided on the governmental websites of Botswana, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa and Uganda regarding their responsibility for regulating, accrediting and monitoring TVET. These governments have developed standards for TVET, the quality requirements for which they (partially) publish and for which they (partially) monitor compliance.

Approaches to the management of TVET that are worth supporting and developing can be found across the U-publications of the above countries, which inform our discussion of the issues in this chapter. Although there is research on the general management of TVET, there is little specific research on the TVET standards (including the appropriateness, development and testing of such standards). Generally speaking, we can therefore say that the TVET standards are not informed by specific research.

Researching standards is a promising field for future research. For example, Joy Papier (University of Western Cape, South Africa) noted that South Africa is far ahead in terms of policies on teacher development because the country standardised its teacher education. According to her, more and more countries in SSA are trying to standardise the qualifications. We note that further discussion of the need for research on policy is presented in Chapter 14, based on the insights of participants in the SCR.

As in the other chapters, the following sections present individual aspects of the chapter summary above.

12.1. National qualifications frameworks for TVET

The table below lists national qualifications frameworks (NQFs) for TVET from the countries in SSA that have published this information. These policies were available on public websites; further policies may potentially be obtained from Ministries directly. Some of the current qualification frameworks were introduced in the early 2000s. Since then, there has been an increase in the number of countries establishing their national standards in recent years.

Table 12.1. Qualifications frameworks and TVET-related national standards in SSA

Country and Year of Publication	Qualification Framework / Standards	Published or established by
Botswana, 1997	NPVET—National Policy on Vocational Education and Training (†Government of Botswana, 1997)	MLHA—Ministry of Labour and Home Affairs
Botswana, 2005	BNVQF—Botswana National Vocational Qualifications Framework (†Government of Botswana, 2005)	BOTA—Botswana Training Authority
Botswana, 2016	NCQF—National Credit and Qualifications Framework (†Government of Botswana, 2016)	BQA—Botswana Qualification Authority

Ghana, 2012	NTVETQF—National Technical and Vocational Education and Training Qualifications Framework (†Government of Ghana, estimated 2012)	COTVET—Council for Technical and Vocational Education and Training
Kenya, 2014	KNQF Act—Kenya National Qualifications Framework Act N° 22 (†Government of Kenya, 2014)	National Council of Law
Kenya, 2015	National Industrial Training Standards (†Government of Kenya, 2015)	NITA—National Industrial Training Authority
Kenya, 2018	CBETA Standards and Guidelines—TVETA Competency-Based Education and Training and Assessment Standards & Guidelines (†Government of Kenya, 2018)	TVETA—Technical and Vocational Education and Training Authority
Malawi, 2015	National Education Standards—primary and secondary education (†Government of Malawi, 2015)	MoEST—Ministry of Education, Science and Technology
Mauritius, 2001	MQA Act—Mauritius Qualifications Authority Act No. 42 (†Government of Mauritius, 2001)	Federal Government
Nigeria, 1985	Education Act No. 16 (National Minimum Standards and Establishment of Institutions) (†Government of Nigeria, 1985)	Federal Government
Nigeria	NID Curricula—National Vocational Certificates – curriculum and course specifications (†Government of Nigeria, accessed 2018)	NBTE—National Board for Technical Education
South Africa, 2006	Further Education and Training Act No. 16 (†Government of South Africa, 2006)	Federal Government
South Africa, 2008	NQF Act—National Qualifications Framework No. 67 (†Government of South Africa, 2009)	Federal Government
South Africa, 2013	NQF Level 1—Regulation on the Assessment Process and Procedures for Adult Education and Training (AET) (†Government of South Africa, 2013)	DHET—Department of Higher Education and Training
Uganda, 2014	UBTEB rules on the assessment of competences and conduct of business, technical and vocational examinations in Uganda (†Government of Uganda, 2014)	UBTEB—Uganda Business and Technical Examinations Board

Uganda, 2012	Uganda Vocational Qualifications Framework (UVQF) summary of generic level descriptors (†Government of Uganda, 2012)	DIT—Directorate of Industrial Training
Uganda	Qualifications Framework (†Directorate of Industrial Training, accessed 2018)	DIT—Directorate of Industrial Training

12.1.1. Scope of the standards

In the vast majority of countries, the national standards documents are relevant to TVET institutions. They set the minimum requirements for the classification, registration and accreditation of national qualifications and certificates.

The East African Common Higher Education Area was cited as an organisation that could eventually propel the harmonisation of TVET in the member countries with different NQFs. However, UNESCO’s report on the status of TVET in the South African Development Community (SADC) region warns that although NQFs can make a contribution to TVET reform,

“they cannot transform overnight problems with limited progression, lack of recognition of prior learning or integration of informal sector training into a national skills system” (†UNESCO, 2013).

The standards apply to private and state education providers and are monitored by government agencies (Table 12.1), which are responsible for the accreditation of institutions and TVET programmes. One of the tasks of the institutions is also to make TVET popular among students. To this end, they conduct public relations work and provide information on career paths that are possible after choosing certain courses.

12.1.2. Pedagogical approaches promoted in qualification frameworks

Where the pedagogical approach was discussed in the official documents of Kenya, Ghana, Uganda, Tanzania and South Africa, competency-based education was consistently the preferred choice. However, this approach, and the concept of competence behind it, are not explicitly mentioned in the research papers we reviewed. Nevertheless, the documents are clearly set within on a competency-based model which reflects an Anglo-Saxon educational tradition (†Deissinger, 2013), and not on the paradigm of TVET that exists in Germany (†ibid.) as recommended by the German Kultusminister Konferenz⁴ since 2017 (†KMK, 2017).

Generally speaking, there is little specific research on the pedagogical models or indeed the competency-based model. For country-specific details, we thus have to rely on information made available by the various authorities. For example, in Uganda, the Directorate of Industrial Training (DIT) is responsible for defining the Ugandan framework for TVET and decided to take a competency-based approach. The Uganda Business and Technical Examinations Board (UBTEB) sets the criteria for the assessment of vocational skills in guidelines, and monitors their implementation. The Vocational Qualifications Framework (UVQF) and the institutional framework for the promotion and coordination

of Business Technical Vocational Education and Training (Uganda BTVET) were established in 2008. State-certified training courses are therefore required to adopt the competence orientation. However, this does not rule out the possibility that private education providers will turn to other basic pedagogical positions in TVET. We do note that in Uganda, the most important representatives of industry were involved in the introduction of competence-oriented TVET. They have clear interest in the implementation of a competence-based curriculum by vocational training providers, and want to ensure on-the-job training (in production) in the future and make it a compulsory part of examinations (DIT, UBTEB).

Our literature survey encountered a few more references debating the development, implementation and assessment of a competency-based curriculum (e.g., †[Namibia: Shindi, 2017](#); see also, †[Rwanda: Muraraneza & Mtshali, 2018](#); †[Rwanda: van Halsema & Mulder, 2017](#); †[Mulder, et al., 2007](#)). However, one of the publications discussed the underlying theoretical concept of competency-based education.

12.1.3. Qualifications frameworks exclusively dedicated to TVET, and sector strategic plans

We found specific TVET qualification frameworks in three countries: Botswana, Ghana and Uganda. The Botswana National Vocational Qualifications Framework (†[Government of Botswana, 2005](#)) is exclusively dedicated to TVET, having no links to general or higher education. In Ghana, the National Technical and Vocational Education and Training Qualifications Framework (NTVETQF) prescribes a nine-level qualifications framework for the TVET sector, describing the knowledge, skills and attitudes that should be expected from students for each one of the nine levels. These first six levels are considered to be pre-tertiary education. The Ministry of Education's Council for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (COTVET) in Ghana, is considering opening up the first two levels to the informal sector. In other words, COTVET is seeking to include apprentices in informal TVET relationships within framework. The remaining three levels require a demonstration of high levels of conceptual knowledge, as well as supervisory and management capabilities.

Our internet search also revealed strategic plans designed specifically for the TVET sectors in Botswana (†[ETSSP 2015–2020—Education & Training Sector Strategic Plan](#)), Kenya (†[TVET Strategic Plan 2018–2022](#)), Uganda (†[BTVET Strategic Plan 2011–2020](#)) and South Africa. The latter has also developed the Human Resource Development Strategy for South Africa 2010–2030 (†[Government of South Africa, 2010](#)) and an integrated strategic planning framework for teacher education and development 2011–2025 (†[Government of South Africa, 2011](#)).

Focussing on Kenya, Lawrence Mukhongo Manyonge (Technical University of Mombasa, Kenya) mentioned that a number of structures have been put in place that support TVET in that country. He cites as examples the presence of TEVETA and a permanent secretary dedicated to TVET at the Ministry of Education, the TVET Act 2013 (and the creation of TVET Authority), the proposition for the creation of a Kenya National Qualifications

Authority (KNQA), and a NQF providing 10 levels of education (up to PhD). For Miki Gilbert Ngwaneh (Vocational Centre for International Development, Cameroon), Kenya's model of polytechnics, and how they equip students with skills, is distinctive. He added that their polytechnics are based on the UK model.

12.2. State regulation of TVET

As we have previously noted our internet search and policy analysis have shown that most SSA countries have government bodies dedicated to accrediting TVET programmes and institutions. These accreditations are typically renewed every few years, with validity varying from a minimum of two years to a maximum of five years. The exact length depends on the country and the course that is being provided.

In addition to our analysis of the research, we can draw on statements from SCR participants who commented on state regulations. For Gabriel Konayuma (Ministry of Higher Education, Zambia), Malawi has done well by having a more organised framework for financing the TVET system. In terms of Tanzania, he highlights their decentralisation process, deeming that they have done well. Emmanuel C. Osinem (Department of Vocational Teacher Education, University of Nigeria) believes that Tanzania gives more attention to TVET, emphasising the fact that they have a Federal Minister for the sector.

Table 12.2 below lists the state TVET regulations that were found by our internet search, in addition to what was retrieved through the literature review. Following the table is a brief description of the registration, accreditation and monitoring processes in those countries. Notably, Nigeria stands out for the number of documents it has published over the years and the amount of information available. This has given us a better understanding of the regulatory process involved in Nigeria's TVET than in other countries.

Table 12.2. State TVET regulations per country, and year of publication

Country	Year of Publication	State TVET regulations
Ghana	2007	Polytechnic Law (†Government of Ghana, 2007)
Kenya	2016	Guidelines for Registration of Training Providers (†Government of Kenya, 2016)
	2013	Technical and Vocational Education and Training Act No. 29 of 2013 (†Government of Kenya, 2013)
	2015	Technical and Vocational Education and Training Act Regulations (Government of Kenya, 2015)
Mauritius	2009	Mauritius Qualifications Authority regulations (†Government of Mauritius, 2009)

Nigeria	1985	Education (National Minimum Standards and Establishment of Institutions) Act No. 16 (↑Government of Nigeria, 1985)
	1987	Educational Correspondence Colleges Accreditation Act No. 32 (↑Government of Nigeria, 1987)
	2014	Guidelines and Procedures for the Establishment of Private Technical and Technological Institutions (↑Government of Nigeria, 2014)
	2006	Guidelines for Establishment and Operation of Production Unit in Technical Colleges (↑Government of Nigeria, 2006)
	2007	Standards and Criteria for Approval of Programmes in Vocational Enterprise Institutions (VEI) (↑Government: Nigeria, 2007)
South Africa	2015	National Policy on Community Education and Training Colleges (↑Government of South Africa, 19 2015)
	2011	Integrated Strategic Planning Framework for Teacher Education and Development in South Africa, 2011–2025 (↑Government of South Africa, 2011)
Uganda	2013	Guidelines for establishing, licensing, registering and classification of private schools/institutions in Uganda (↑Government of Uganda, 2013)

12.2.1. Regulation in Botswana

In Botswana, the Botswana Training Authority (BOTA) works in parallel to the Botswana Qualifications Authority (BQA) in the regulation of training providers. The latter registers and accredits learning programmes and assessors, as well as awarding bodies and moderators. As specified by Botswana’s TVET Act, the BOTA is mandated to

“accredit, register and monitor both public and private training institutions to ensure adherence to the required standard and quality of training and to minimise variability between the training institutions” and has the power to *“accredit, monitor and evaluate the implementation of programme courses for a comprehensive development of the individual, the economy and the society”* ([↑Government of Botswana, 1998:5](#)).

The BOTA strived to develop standards that were based on both industry’s and learners’ needs. Its Learning Programmes service provides several guidelines for quality assurance of school-based and work-based TVET. (For further information, see Section 12.3.2.)

12.2.2. Regulation in Nigeria

The UNEVOC country profile report on Nigeria's TVET system provides a good insight into how it regulates TVET providers and how it conducts education quality assessments. The report highlights that accrediting agencies usually take into consideration four basic standards when carrying out programme accreditation: the students, the physical facilities, the staff and the available funding. Some agencies add the quality of teaching and learning, which according to UNEVOC *"is actually the interaction of the four standards in the implementation of the curricula"* (†UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2012: 11).

The functions of the National Board for Technical Education (†NBTE) include

"the establishment and maintenance of minimum standards in polytechnics and other technical institutions in the Federation", and the "accreditation of academic programmes in all technical and vocational education (TVE) institutions for the purpose of award of national certificates and diplomas and other similar awards" (†Government of Nigeria, accessed Dec. 2018).

UNESCO-UNEVOC's account of the accreditation process in Nigeria was the closest and only illustration we could retrieve on how this process might take place. It is described as follows:

"Accreditation visit to a specific discipline is usually undertaken by a panel of experts in the professional [...] area drawn from the academia, industry, and relevant professional bodies, under NBTE's coordination. The team normally uses the NBTE minimum guide curriculum and programme specifications, as the minimum reference, and the NBTE's programmes evaluation form, as a guide." (†UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2012: 11)

Moreover, through the internet search, we identified that Nigeria's Federal Education Quality Assurance Service (FIS) fulfils its mandate of ensuring *"optimal attainment in all Institutions below tertiary level"* and *"uniform standard and quality control of instructional activities"* by carrying out regular inspection and continuous supervision of schools (†Government of Nigeria, accessed 2018). Indeed, the FIS has a whole school evaluation inspectorate division (I-WSE), as well as a curriculum and pedagogy (I-C&P) division. To carry out such inspections, it has one Zonal Office in each of the six geopolitical zones of the country as well as 36 state offices. Despite having the structure and regulations in place, some difficulties in keeping inspections up-to-date should be expected, since at the time the data for this report was collected, FIS's website stated that there was

"only one substantive Director heading South-East zones; while the state offices are headed by Coordinating Inspectors who are normally Deputy Directors. However, only 20 state offices are manned by Deputy Directors" (†ibid.).

Additionally, in 2007, registration of all professionally qualified teachers became mandatory, and in-service seminars and workshops started to be introduced all over the country with the aim of training teachers and qualifying unqualified teachers. UNESCO-UNEVOC states that

“generally, the Teachers’ Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) undertakes the accreditation of the courses and programmes of all establishments that prepare individuals intending to become teachers in Nigeria” (†UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2012: 10).

12.2.3. Regulation in Tanzania

In Tanzania, the registration of public and private institutions and the accreditation of their programmes fall under the mandates of the Vocational Education and Training Authority (VETA) and the National Council for Technical Education (NACTE) (†UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2016:13). As the country’s TVET authority, VETA is responsible for setting the sub-sector standards, developing curricula, carrying out assessment and awarding certifications. Thus,

“it is the government body that set the standards for TVET institutions – registering and accrediting them and auditing them for compliance” (†Government of Tanzania, accessed Dec. 2018).

The Authority website states that, by 2018, there were a total of 573 registered centres in Tanzania, 29 of which are owned by VETA.

12.2.4. Regulation in Uganda

In Uganda, the 2013 Guidelines for Licensing and Registering of Private Schools lists the requirements to accredit schools. The document has a section on the requirements for operating TVET providers, in which it states that

“BTVET [business, technical, vocational education and training] schools/ institutions at the time of registration will be required to have in place all the Basic Requirements and Minimum Standards (Indicators for Educational Institutions) as contained in the Directorate of Education Standards (DES) booklet (November 2000, BRMS)” (†Government of Uganda, 2013:11).

12.3. Quality assurance and accreditation of TVET

In some countries, the parliamentary acts establishing the TVET authorities also list the criteria for accrediting, monitoring and evaluating TVET institutions and / or programmes. An example of this is the Kenya National Qualifications Framework Act (KNQF Act), which also includes the delineation of a system of competencies and attainment of national qualifications by KNQA. The Kenya Qualifications Framework establishes the standards for the recognition of qualifications obtained in and outside of the country, with the aim of facilitating mobility and progression within education, training and career paths. In other countries, however, the qualifications frameworks and the regulations and assessment of TVET providers and / or programmes have been developed by different state authorities altogether. Following Table 12.3 below, on regulating and monitoring responsibilities by country and state authority, is a brief description of the monitoring of TVET standards in each of the countries mentioned in that table.

12.3.1. Functions and responsibilities of state authorities

The state authority in charge of monitoring standards and qualifications is usually the TVET authority and/or the quality assurance authority if the country has one. The details are not always clear regarding how the monitoring and evaluation systems are structured, and how data are collected and analysed.⁵ Regarding policy planning related to TVET standards, each government body is generally expected to advise the Ministry of Education on matters within their mandate. Hence, the same institutions are repeatedly drawn upon in each country. In summary, the bodies responsible for monitoring TVET standards in the following countries are:

Table 12.3. Regulating and monitoring responsibilities by country and state authority

Country	State authority	Functions and responsibilities
Botswana	↑BOTA	Definition and regulation of national TVET standards; Registration of development in the field of educational provision; Definition of TVET regulations; Advisor for the Minister on TVET matters.
	↑BQA	Monitoring and evaluation of TVET quality assurance standards; Advisor for the Minister on quality standards matters.
Ghana	↑TVED	Education Division (TVED) is one of the ten (10) Divisions of the Ghana Education Service (GES) Headquarters responsible for implementing pre-tertiary Technical and Vocational Education under the Ministry of Education (MoE); Monitoring and evaluation of public Technical Training Institutes and private TVET providers; Guidelines for examinations and certifications in TVET.
	↑COTVET	Formulates national policies for skills development; It is expected that the tasks of the TVED will be transferred to COTVET in the future.
Kenya	↑TVETA	Registration, licensing and accreditation of institutions, programmes and trainers; Management of the TVET National Quality Assurance System; Determination of national TVET objectives; Advises government in all matters regarding training.
	↑NITA	Inspection of industrial training providers.
	↑TVET CDACC	Designs and develops CBET curricula and carries out competence assessment and certification.

Nigeria	↑FIS	Monitoring and evaluation of education quality; Inspection and continuous supervision of instructional activities in schools; Collection of information on problems and difficulties encountered by teachers and institutions.
	↑EPRD, MoE	Policy planning for the education sector
South Africa	↑DHET, ↑UMALUSI (Council for Quality Assurance in General and Further Education and Training)	Accreditation of education providers Promotion of education quality improvement Assessment and certification of learners' achievement
Tanzania	↑VETA	Accreditation of education providers Definition of TVET regulations and guidelines concerning syllabi, examination and certification Inspection and supervision of TVET centres
Uganda	↑DIT	Development of occupational standards Assessment and certification of students Assessment of education programmes Accreditation of assessment centres and assessors
	↑DES	Inspection of schools and institutions Evaluation of education programmes and institutions Publication of reports on education quality and the dissemination of good practices

12.3.2. Monitoring of TVET standards in Botswana

In Botswana, data collection and monitoring of the TVET system is carried out by two agencies of the Ministry of Education and Skills Development: the Botswana Training Authority (↑BOTA) and the Botswana Qualifications Authority (↑BQA). The country's TVET Act assigned the BOTA the power to make regulations for any matter affecting apprenticeship training (↑Government of Botswana, 1998). This includes prescribing and regulating national training standards for the various qualification levels within the National Vocational Qualifications Framework, and requesting information from any training provider in the country where it deems this necessary in order to carry out its functions. On the other hand, the BQA coordinates quality assurance from early childhood to tertiary level by regulating compliance through monitoring and evaluation. Accordingly,

the BQA sets up the criteria for designing, developing, implementing and reviewing the national common quality assurance platform for the country's education system as a whole. Additionally, it is expected to advise the Minister on all matters pertaining to its functions. This includes the development of policy and criteria for work-based teaching and learning, the recognition of prior learning, and the credit accumulation and transfer system.

12.3.3. Monitoring of TVET standards in Ghana

In Ghana, TVET quality assurance is the responsibility of the Ministry of Education's Council for Technical and Vocational Education and Training ([↑COTVET](#)). The Council intends to issue annual reports on the state of skills development in the country in 2021, and has the objective of formulating national policies for skills development across the broad spectrum of pre-tertiary and tertiary education: formal, informal and non-formal. Currently, The Ghana Education Service (GES)⁶ has a Technical and Vocational Education Division (TVED)⁷ in charge of the monitoring and evaluation of 26 public Technical Training Institutes (TTIs) and private TVET providers. Likewise, at this moment, TVED develop and review the curriculum of TVET programmes, conducts TVET examinations, and awards certificates. We note that such responsibilities are planned to be shifted to COTVET. The Ministry of Education also includes the National Board for Professional and Technician Examinations (NABPTEX)⁸, responsible for evaluation, assessment and certification for non-university tertiary institutions.

12.3.4. Monitoring of TVET standards in Kenya

In Kenya, under the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology ([↑MoEST](#)), the Technical and Vocational Education and Training Authority (TVETA) is responsible for implementation of the TVET national quality assurance system. It covers 14 areas, including industrial attachment / internship; the condition of the learning environment; adequacy of tools and equipment for training; management of examinations; internal quality assurance mechanisms; and the professional and pedagogical qualifications of trainers. MoEST's TVET Curriculum Development, Assessment and Certification Council (TVET CDACC) is mandated

"to undertake design and development of curricula for the training institutions' examination, assessment and competence certification and advise the Government [on related matters]" ([↑TVET Curriculum Development, Assessment and Certification Council. Kenya, 2015:1](#)).

Finally, the responsibilities of the National Industrial Training Authority ([↑NITA](#)) includes inspection of training providers. It sets the standards and guidelines for internal and external quality assurance in industrial training and publishes the list of approved training providers on its website. The latest list was released in May 2020 ([↑National Industrial Training Authority, 2020](#)). A code of conduct for registered training providers can also be found on the Authority's website.

Kenya developed another instrument for monitoring with the Kenya National Qualification Framework Act (KNQF Act, 2014). The Framework provides for the registration of qualifications by awarding institutions. It also develops policies to guide education and training, and policies for the development of training standards in all levels of training. In implementing this Framework, KNQA works together with regulators including the Commission for University Education (CUE), TVETA and professional bodies.

Kenya is also making use of the TVET Act 2013, which provides for the accreditation of institutions, programmes and trainers by TVETA. TVETA also develops standards and guidelines for the implementation of training in Kenya, such as CBETA, the trainers qualification framework and the minimum standards for infrastructure and equipment. It has established a National Polytechnic and a centre of excellence. In addition, TVETA has developed the Kenya National Quality Assurance Framework (KNQAF), an accreditation manual and quality management system for TVET providers.⁹

12.3.5. Monitoring of TVET standards in Nigeria

In Nigeria, ensuring optimal attainment in all institutions below tertiary level is the responsibility of the Federal Education Quality Assurance Service (FEQAS). This is achieved by carrying out regular inspections and continuous supervision of instructional activities in schools, with the aim of assuring uniform standards and quality control of TVET provision. According to Nigeria's Ministry of Education:

"inspection and supervision are two complementary processes in quality assurance and relate to the monitoring of instructional practises and performance of an educational establishment. Inspection concerns evaluation by external agents and is carried out by Federal, as well as State Inspectors. Supervision is an internal process carried out by School functionaries such as the principal, vice principals or heads of departments or other state-designated personnel" († Government of Nigeria, accessed May 2020).¹⁰

The FIS is hence responsible for designing, monitoring and evaluating instruments for measuring education quality. It has the mandate of obtaining information on the problems and difficulties encountered by teachers and institutions, and putting forward practical solutions to them. According to †UNESCO-UNEVOC (2012), Nigeria's TVET was faced with a lot of issues, one of them being a lack of efficient educational monitoring and evaluation procedures. The report states that FIS is also responsible for ensuring linkages with

"the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council, the faculties of education, institutes of education and other national and international bodies on development in curriculum content, delivery and pedagogy practices as they apply to secondary technical and vocational education" (†ibid.:9).

9 †Technical and Vocational Education and Training Authority (TVETA), Home, available at www.tveta.go.ke

10 †Government of Nigeria, Education, available at <https://nigeria.gov.ng/programs-initiatives/education/>.

Policy planning, however, falls under the Educational Planning Research and Development department of the Ministry of Education.

12.3.6. Monitoring of TVET standards in South Africa

In South Africa, the General and Further Education and Training Quality Assurance Council ([↑Government of South Africa, 2001](#)) accredits providers, promotes education quality improvement and ensures providers adopt quality management systems for learner achievement. The council also assures the quality of learner assessment at exit points and issues certificates of learner achievement. Thus, it is the State authority in charge of monitoring standards and qualifications in South Africa. Its responsibilities include the maintenance of a data bank, reporting to the Minister on the performance of departments of education as providers, and recommending the necessary steps to rectify any of its deficiencies. Finally, the Council is responsible for regulating the relationship between the national Department of Education, the South African Qualifications Authority, Education and Training Quality Assurance Bodies, and providers.

In South Africa, responsibility for teacher training is distributed among various ministries. The Department of Higher Education and Training ([↑DHET](#)) and the Basic Education departments in South Africa published a strategic plan to provide a framework for teacher education with the aim of improving the country's education quality. The Government worked towards empowering principals to manage their schools and be held accountable for maintaining a high standard of education, entering them into performance contracts with clear targets. The plan expected that the government would track teachers' performance

“through the independently moderated annual national assessments in all public primary schools” ([↑Government of South Africa, 2011:6](#)).

However, the last national assessment report we could find at the point of data collection for this report was written in 2014.

12.3.7. Monitoring of TVET standards in Uganda

The Ministry of Education and Sports ([↑MoES](#)) in Uganda has a Directorate of Industrial Training ([↑DIT](#)). Its responsibilities include: the development of occupational standards, the assessment of training packages, the accreditation of assessment centres and assessors, and the administration of competency-based assessments and certification of successful candidates. Also under Uganda's Ministry of Education and Sports is the Directorate of Education Standards (DES), which is responsible for setting, reviewing and monitoring quantitative and qualitative standards in the education sector. Its key functions are the planning and development of inspections of schools and institutions, evaluations of the effectiveness of education programmes and institutions, and issuing reports on the quality of education and the dissemination of best practice. Thus, it has published a series of six booklets guiding education professionals on how to improve the experiences and achievements of learners in schools, and of technical/vocational institutions, by focusing on their needs ([↑ Government of Uganda, 2012](#)). DES' work

covers all the districts in Uganda and both public and private schools and institutions. The Directorate also provides professional and policy advice to the MoES, local governments, schools and other institutions such as the UNEB, the National Curriculum Development Centre and the Education Service Commission.

12.4. Chapter bibliography

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